

1 **Characterization and causal model of the holistic** 2 **dynamics of the integral sustainability of the agrifood** 3 **system**

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13 **Abstract**

14 The transformation of the food and industrial agricultural production system into adaptative and sustainable
15 systems capable of being productive within social, environmental, and economic limits are relevant to reducing
16 the risk to food security and economic growth. However, the analysis structure the effect of these variables in
17 sustainable environments is unknown, considering technology and processes as variables of the equivalent
18 critical level as those already mentioned. The purpose of this study is to design a model that allows the
19 characterization and causal model of the holistic dynamics of the agri-food sector, from the determination of
20 sustainable variables from a sustainable and integral systemic approach. Tools such as the viable systems model
21 are used to analyze the dynamics and generate the balanced scorecard, to which the items of learning and
22 continuous improvement are added. Finally, the impact of the principles of sustainability versus the variation
23 of sustainability in the agri-food system is recognized, and useful to determine the appropriate levels that

24 guarantee the balance between the foundations of circularity. This model from a systemic approach can be
25 adopted by agronomists and scientists to design alternative strategies for the management of food sustainability.

26 **Introduction**

27 In the agri-food sector, activities of great importance are developed due to their contribution to the
28 economy and to human life itself, in consequence the interest in studying them from the perspective
29 of holistic dynamics [1], that is, from the changes and interactions that arise in its whole, constituted
30 by the flow of people, information, energy, materials, among other structures and organizations, and
31 that through its activity issues of economic, social, environmental, technological utility arise from the
32 execution of the processes it demands, affecting the health, well-being and balance of an entire local,
33 regional, national and international ecosystem [2,3].

34 However, considering its productive activity, human beings are the ones who exploit the land and
35 other resources causing an effect on the environment; the space occupied for crops represents 37% of
36 the arable land surface and the use of water for these corresponds to almost 2/3 of the total area of
37 arable land [4,5]. An effect on the environment is pollution by nitrates, phosphates, and pesticides,
38 acting as a source of production of greenhouse gases, methane, and nitrous oxide which affects air
39 and water quality [6,7].

40 The poor management of the land leads to stress which produces degradation by salinization, excess
41 water extraction and contamination of groundwater by agrochemical residues. This is due to the use
42 of quantities higher than those needed by crops and generating an imbalance in the ecosystem,
43 affecting the environment, productive capacity, economy, and society [8–10].

44 According to the studies of Benabderrazik et al., food security and economic growth in the regions
45 must be associated with a balanced interaction between social and economic well-being and the
46 protection of natural resources, since an intensification of activities in these sectors leads to
47 unsustainability, putting at risk the general well-being of the population and the productivity of the

48 region, affecting the ecological environment. These components interact in a nonlinear, complex, and
49 dynamic way, so it is pertinent to analyze the feedback received by the system to offer sustainable
50 and adaptable solutions to environment situations[11].

51 The theory of adaptive systems represents an effective framework for the analysis of the dynamics of
52 systems in terms of their transitions, as cyclical evolution seeks equilibrium as changes arise, the agri-
53 food sector articulates a type of complex adaptive system in which there is an exchange of matter,
54 energy and information internally and with external structures, through the ability to self-manage
55 corresponding to its systemic functionality [12].

56 The incorporation of strategies such as life cycle analysis (LCA) allows the development of products
57 in a conscious way about the impacts they generate in each of their stages, from design to final
58 disposal, which leads to reasonable agri-food production, improving their environmental, economic,
59 health and well-being properties, this with the help of technologies that contribute to this end, also
60 improving the levels of efficiency and productivity of the processes by making better use and
61 disposition of the resources that will have an impact on the accessibility of future generations [13,14].

62 Through the application of the circular economy from the perspective of reducing, reusing, and
63 recycling in work models with the influence of eco-design and the use of raw materials from
64 renewable sources, a considerable reduction in waste generation is expected, favoring society, the
65 environment, the economy and the efficiency of processes guaranteeing the sustainability of
66 operations from the management of technology and information [15,16].

67 This article aims to characterize and causal model holistic dynamics from an integral sustainability
68 approach to the agri-food system. As a complex adaptive system, it is relevant to identify the elements
69 and relationships that make up the system, then graph the dynamics, considering the interconnections
70 of the variables, followed by an analysis from the model of viable systems for the conclusion of a

71 balanced scorecard that serves as a support tool for the management of the improvement and learning
72 of the system, that is, the evolution of the system towards the objectives set.

73 **Literature review**

74 In the agri-food sector, the production, distribution and consumption of food is one of the sectors
75 most affected by the crisis of climate imbalance [5], and unfavorable practices in its operation altering
76 its holistic dynamics [17], which has a direct impact on sustainability reducing the opportunity to
77 guarantee better levels of health, food and an environment and an efficient level of water, air and soil
78 for future generations, however it is the agro-industrial sector that can most help improve conditions
79 regarding environmental problems that are already worrying today [18,19]. In Europe, research and
80 development are being carried out to increase the value of unsuitable food materials for human
81 consumption (wrappings) and to consider food waste and residues, focusing on economic and
82 environmental variables [20].

83 Riemens et al., focused their research on the holistic improvement of herbicide chemicals to increase
84 the sustainability of the agricultural sector, because they are critical in the management of weeds that
85 compete with crops for resources such as light, water, nutrients and visible space, affecting crop yield
86 and the environment and human health [21].

87 Water scarcity is another factor that conditions the integral sustainability of the agri-food system,
88 making use of water resources without considering the effects that lead to socioeconomic problems
89 and degradation of resources; therefore, it is necessary to study the underlying variables in the agri-
90 food system to avoid unforeseen effects [11]. Water is one of the resources that is affected by climate
91 change, and high temperatures have achieved the scarcity of this resource due to low rainfall and
92 dryness or, on the other hand, the large amount of rain in short periods of time overflows because you
93 drag particles that pollute bodies of water such as rivers, gaps, among others putting at risk the quality
94 and productivity of the activity of the agri-food sector, other aspects are the wells of illegal

95 underground aquifers diverting the courses of the aquifer sources or contaminating them by the
96 mismanagement of the same, highlighting the crisis of governance in the sector [22].

97 Diogo et al. highlighted the importance of the social component within the sustainability model; in
98 their research, they demonstrated that it is the least developed element and that no evaluation tool
99 allows us to recognize the dynamic interaction of ecosystems with communities [23].

100 On the other hand, Cook et al. argue that expansionism has dehumanized agricultural activities
101 influenced by power and the desire to improve productivity by ignoring the significant contribution
102 of farmers, who must adapt to new technologies or give up their labor, which the authors point out
103 as unfair from the social point of view, recognizing also that change in complex systems must include
104 commitment to the members existing, which carry out the day-to-day practices in that system.
105 Additionally, they state that the work of women is minimized in the implementation of the
106 expansionist concept and that the results in terms of the productivity of the sector and the welfare of
107 farmers are not evident [24].

108 However, works such as [25] consider expansionism as a tool that can allow the fulfillment of SDG
109 2 of the United Nations, in which it is projected to end extreme poverty and hunger, consider that
110 this strategy of transfer of knowledge and technology to farmers can contribute to the solution of
111 problems specific to the work and the environment in which it takes place, but it also argue that it is
112 necessary to put aside the attention on specific behavioral changes and move it to the creation of
113 awareness, with which learning will become more productive. In addition, it adds that sustainability,
114 behavioral change, and technology adoption are less relevant than increasing farmers' self-confidence
115 engaging and playing a role in the agricultural development process.

116 Studies have been carried out to understand the elements that obstruct the ability to exercise practices
117 that contribute to nature conservation. These studies are based on innovation systems approaches,
118 with real emphasis on the development of multiscale frameworks that are specific to each

119 environment and relevant to evaluate in an integrated way the sustainability of changes in agricultural
120 intensity [26].

121 The tools available for the application of systems that are linked to the circular economy are aimed
122 at large companies, leaving aside SMEs, who to a lesser extent are also aware of the need for the
123 transformation of the productive system that has visions about the general welfare of society, the
124 economy of the regions and the conservation of the environment; However, Industry 4.0 is already
125 offering sustainable practices focused on the circular economy in these organizations [27,28].

126 Life cycle in the agri-food sector. The processes are given by two components, one biological and the
127 other technical [29]. The first is capable of being reintegrated into the biosphere with which it is
128 intended to create alternatives of waste instead of accessing processes of biochemical extraction,
129 composting and reincorporation into the biosphere, while the second is destined to be revalued
130 without entering the biosphere, since at the end of its useful life they could be repaired, reuse,
131 ultimately remanufactures recycling to avoid extraction of new raw materials [30,31].

132 It is necessary from the moment of design to consider the elements that will be part of this and the
133 appropriate technologies to minimize its impact in terms of abiotic resources, acidification,
134 eutrophication, global warming, depletion of the ozone layer, human toxicity, ecotoxicity in fresh
135 water and soil, formation of photochemical oxidants, which brings an imbalance in ecosystems
136 affecting the environment, health and therefore society, economic impacts for its repair and affecting
137 the efficiency of production processes in general of the agro-industrial sector, mainly those of a
138 biological nature [7].

139 In the absence of efficient design of sustainable processes and products under the framework of
140 circularity, there are aggravating situations such as food waste, which currently accounts for a third
141 of total food. It is estimated that edible food waste in the European Union is approximately 89 million

142 tons each year, of which 42% is responsible for households, 39% for food manufacturing processes,
143 14% for catering services, and 5% for the distribution sector [31].

144 Product Lifecycle Management (PLM) as a tool for managing the life cycle of a product allows
145 visualization of the development and progress in projects of the creation of products and services,
146 being pertinent to know in advance the costs and other information of interest of that product,
147 allowing a better vision about the best options, in such a way that it is of help to make efficient
148 decisions, which also does not interfere negatively with the environment. This tool facilitates the
149 integration of project stakeholders by making available the information and traceability of this at each
150 stage of its development [20,32–34].

151 PLM is a vital tool from conception to final disposal of the product [35]. This process occurs in 3
152 phases, beginning of life, half, and the end of the life of the product itself, with which it coincides
153 [36]. Additionally, Salonitis and Stavropoulos argues that the conventional PLM system only focuses
154 on the first phase, so it suggests an extension to the other phases. Recognizing other limitations
155 highlights the integration of different tools in a digital platform, the interoperability of systems and
156 devices both internal and external, and the number of files and data exchanges between stakeholders
157 in all phases of the life cycle [35].

158 On the other hand, PLM contributes to the transition of Industry 4.0 from the digitalization of
159 processes to better control, monitoring it from good traceability and follow-up practices for better
160 decision making. In addition to Industry 4.0 tools, such as artificial intelligence, IoT, machine
161 learning, big data, it should be integrated into the agri-food sector and precision agriculture to
162 optimize productivity and resource efficiency [28,37–39].

163 LCA and the circular economy led to cleaner production spaces. The first contributes to the
164 quantification of the environmental impacts present in the study system [40] while the second helps
165 to identify and define the scenarios to improve the characteristics of such a system [41], which is an

166 iterative process that allows measurement of good practices and their real effects [15,40]. However,
167 authors such as Poponi et al. argue that LCA study proposals have been criticized for not being
168 suitable for specific products, since it is a methodology designed for products at a general level [42].

169 In general, the processes require a focus on meeting the United Nations Sustainable Development
170 Goals (SDGs), in which SDG 12 focuses on ensuring sustainable consumption and production
171 patterns and includes targets that aim to achieve a more efficient use of resources [43], Therefore, the
172 management and analysis of the life cycle is of great relief because they lead to this compliance from
173 early stages such as design until the product is no longer in a final useful life phase [44].

174 Technological advances today there are tools such as specialized analysis software that due to their
175 complexity are easier to perform through them. Life cycle analysis can be mentioned in several of
176 these programs with some payments and others free and multiplatform, including Air.e LCA, Open
177 LCA, SimaPro, and Eco-it, which are helpful because they allow clarity on the levels of climate
178 change, human toxicity, ecotoxicity, and depletion of biotic resource information of interest to make
179 decisions within the development of products [13].

180 In general, the relevance of tools such as management and life cycle analysis on the sustainable
181 approach and circularity are necessary due to the estimates made for 2050, the year in which there
182 will be an increase between 60 and 70% in food consumption, which compromises the resources
183 available today. For water consumption, for example, it must increase by 30%, while energy demand
184 will have to increase by 45%. However, the transport sector is the one that has the most representation
185 among the registered carbon footprints, with 18% of the total. The transport of food products accounts
186 for between 15 and 30% of the carbon footprint of the food and beverage industry, recognizing that
187 this is a great ally for the distribution, mobility and accessibility of raw materials, inputs, final
188 products, people, and machines among foals that are also part of the agri-food sector [31,45,46].

189 Facing complex problems such as determining the sustainability of a system, the best way to approach
190 them is system dynamics, systemic approach, systemic thinking in general, because being complex,
191 their behaviors are not linear, as a consequence of the feedback loops of the interconnections of the
192 various variables that constitute them as systems. Various authors have employed tools such as causal
193 loop analysis to understand the systemic dynamics of the systems under study and establish possible
194 solutions to support improvement [47–50].

195 **Materials and methods**

196 This work was developed using qualitative and descriptive research within the framework of
197 approach, dynamics, and systemic thinking. The methodology used is based on Sterman’s model [51],
198 which is described in detail in [52]. The implementation process is illustrated in Fig. 1 and begins
199 with identifying a problematic situation in the field of study, drawing on the contributions of Peter
200 Checkland [53,54]. This process acknowledges the gap between perception and reality and aims to
201 address this difference in order to achieve an ideal outcome.

202

203 **Fig. 1 Methodology considering Sterman's essential steps taken from [52]**

204 Then, a dynamic hypothesis is established in which the main variables are identified, and their
205 possible interaction is determined. Having clarity about the variables is necessary to design
206 improvements to the system by creating purposeful systemic models where those variables are
207 interrelated.

208 Then, causal maps and supporting diagrams are made to reflect the interconnections, for which the
209 model of viable systems proposed by Beer [55,56] is also used, from which parameters and estimates
210 of behavior of the system of the variables are established. Due to the modeling, the results are
211 analyzed giving a knowledge of the dynamics of the system allowing us to act on the performance of
212 this system. Through of the application of the methodology proposed by Kaplan and Norton [57] for
213 the creation of the balanced scorecard, favorable and viable changes are estimated according to the
214 specifications of scenarios and the design of improvement policies, which leads to a new reality of
215 the system that will again be contrasted with problematic situations perceived in this new phase and
216 this methodological process will be applied iteratively generate knowledge, learning and continuous
217 improvement of the system under study.

218 For the characterization of the sustainable holistic dynamics of the sector, it was necessary to define
219 the variables of interest that constituted the pentagon of integral sustainability, that is, the five main
220 variables for this model. Subsequently, an evaluation of influence between these variables is carried
221 out, that is, in a range of 1 to 5, with 1 mild effect and 5 strong effects as each of these variables
222 influencing the others. The points awarded are added for each variable, and the highest result indicates
223 which is the variable that receives greater influence from the rest becoming the most affected of the
224 system, so we proceed with the characterization of it for analysis within the system under study
225 considering the other variables of interest of the model.

226 With this evaluation it is also possible to know which variables have the most effects on the others,
227 recognizing the role of systemic analysis that allows connections and integration without ruling out
228 the uniqueness of each variable for a better understanding of the system under study [58].

229 Initially, a systemic causal model of the agro-industrial sector is carried out through the Ithink 8.0
230 modeling software, which allows more precisely to proceed with the diagramming of the model of
231 viable systems, analyzing the relationships of the subsystems that make up the system under study
232 considering the external environment, the information is obtained for the creation of the balanced
233 scorecard in order to identify the variables of interest of the sector from the perspective of integral
234 sustainability, the mission, vision, objectives, indicators, goals and actions to be carried out are
235 established, additionally the following fields are integrated: learning, short-term improvement and
236 long-term improvement the last three items are necessary when the goals and the result of the
237 indicators have a level of deviation greater than 5% with the aim of self-regulating the system so that
238 the established objectives are not affected. Which allows a culture of learning and continuous
239 improvement, remembering that it is an iterative process.

240 Finally, five basic principles are postulated to guarantee integral holistic sustainability, which are
241 analyzed from their link to the process studying their effects on the variables that constitute the
242 pentagon of integral sustainability of the proposed model.

243 **Results**

244 **Identification of variables of interest**

245 The model of sustainable integration in the agri-food sector is given by the different variables that
246 have an impact on the fundamental categories or macro variables of the same within which is the
247 traditional Economy, Society, and Environment; in this work, Technology and Processes are also

248 considered. Each of the above contains different variables that define them within the sector under
249 study as shows the Fig. 2 and distinguishes the sustainable integration model.

250

251

Fig. 2 Elements of the Agrifood Integral Sustainability Model

252 The relationship of the variables between them starting from the conception of a general systemic
253 approach, is perceived from the way they interact producing an effect, hence the need to achieve a
254 balance that allows the harmonious functioning of the system in Fig. 3 shows the causal map and the
255 Fig. 4 show the level of influence between the variables technology, process, environment, society
256 and economy as the main ones of the integral sustainable system model in the agri-food sector.

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Fig. 3 Causal map of integral sustainability variables.

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Fig. 3 Influence of integral sustainability variables on each other.

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In the Figure 3 it is pertinent to observe which is the variable that receives greater influence from the

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others in this case is the variable process, and the variables that most influence the others are: process,

263

technology, and economy. Table 1 shows the values of such evaluation.

264 **Table 1 Level of interaction and influence between the main variables of integral**
 265 **sustainability in the agri-food sector.**

Integral Sustainability Variables	Process	Technology	Environment	Society	Economy	Variable that most affects
Process	5	4	5	4	4	22
Technology	5	5	4	4	4	22
Environment	5	2	5	3	2	17
Society	4	3	3	5	4	19
Economy	4	4	2	3	5	18
Variable that is most affected	23	18	19	19	19	

266 The process variable with a score of 23 is the one that most affects the others, in order of influence
 267 technology, economy, environment and society; on the other hand, those that have the most impact
 268 on the variables with a score of 22 are technology and process. See appendix S1.

269 **Integral sustainable holistic dynamics of the variable process in**
 270 **the agro-industrial sector**

271 It is possible to have two divisions of the materials that circulate in the processes, one biological and
 272 the other technique in words of the Cañoles et al., which first refers to the benefit of the organic matter
 273 that is produced along the food production chain, from primary production to consumption, and the
 274 various organic waste that is generated, such as sludge, agro-industrial byproducts, inedible food
 275 remains, and food waste [29].

276 In contrast, technicians are related to the use of machinery, plastics and other industrial elements used
 277 in agricultural properties.

278 From the Forrester model represented in Fig. 5, the relationship of the variables that are part of the
 279 process in general is evidenced, integrating the biological and technical aspects of the agri-food
 280 sector.

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Fig. 4 Systemic model of sustainable integration in the agri-food sector.

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The model integrates the internal production variables, from the management of resources where the

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planning and control of production are considered, starting from the demand, and the capacity of the

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process to decide whether to import, proceed to produce, considering waste management, reuse and

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recovery of materials integrated with other alternative processes. In addition, the model includes the

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variables that are affected by the waste generated such as water sources, soil, air, and the climate

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present in the environment which can be internal or external; in the same way, it reflects the influence

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of the standards, legislation and current trends in consideration of quality of fertilizers, pest control,

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and quality of soil for planting to name a few that affect the work of supplying inputs and/or raw

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materials. Finally, the influence of market dynamics (economy and society) on demand.

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Holistic and adaptive dynamics of the agro-industrial sector

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based on Beer's viable model integrating the balanced scorecard

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as an iterative process that contributes to learning and continuous

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improvement of the agro-industrial sector.

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Fig. 5 Model of viable systems based on Stafford Beer (S1= System 1, S2=System 2, etc.)

300 Fig. 6 represents the model of viable systems, which is divided into 5 internal systems that are related
 301 to each other and to the external environment. From system 5, policies are created for the conservation
 302 and improvement of economic, social, productive, technological, and economic aspects as the main
 303 categories of the holistic system of integral sustainability. Based on the policies, ethics and values
 304 that characterize the sector, based on the work regulations as a regulatory framework for strategies
 305 and plans in accordance with the mission and vision, this system has a direct relationship with System
 306 4. System 5 establishes the categories of interest of the scorecard; see Table 2.

307 **Table 2 Balanced scorecard designed from the viable system model of the sector under study.**

Category (S5)	Objective (S4)	Indicator (S2)	Meta (S3)	Initiative (S1)
Society				
Environment				
Economy				
Process				
Technology				
Learning:				
Immediate S1 improvements				
Future improvements S4				

308 System 4 the long-term work plans and the objectives presented in the balanced scorecard are
 309 projected considering the entire life cycle, which is necessary to meet the estimated goals considering
 310 the aspects that System 5 safeguards. Therefore, each category established in system 5 is supported
 311 by several objectives for its conservation and improvement as the fundamental pillars of the system.
 312 System 4 feeds and is fed from two inputs, one internal input determined by system 3 and input
 313 external one represented by the environment. From system 3, the information of the deviations or
 314 internal performance of the system in general is received; that is, everything that requires future
 315 improvement is communicated to system 4 so that it makes the relevant strategic structure for an
 316 efficient result. Once it is established, it transfers them again to system 3 so that it lowers them or
 317 delivers them of input to system 1, in which the basic procedures and tasks are executed so that the
 318 system flows and continues its operation.

319 From the external environment, system 4 meets all the requirements of the client, government, and
320 environment among others, considering regulations and trends, which allows better preparation to
321 offer answers and adaptation to the changes that the future holds in terms of sustainability variables,
322 thus reducing the levels of uncertainty before the future.

323 Returning to system 3, this is responsible for the monitoring, control, and measurement of the internal
324 system; in this are the established goals or parameters that must be met to ensure the proper
325 functioning and viability of the system from the regulation of this. The goals are allowed for each
326 objective in each category about the variables of integral sustainability namely, economy, society,
327 environment, process, and technology.

328 This system is supplied by the flow of information from system two; such information is compared
329 with the value of the estimated goal allowing us to calculate and observe the degree of deviation of
330 the real results of the system from its ideals.

331 The results of the deviations are averaged by category and plotted according to the Pentagon's
332 sustainability; the categories that in the graph indicate a deviation over 5% will require an analysis
333 for their prompt performance improvement and it will be necessary to make a graph for each category
334 individually. With the graphs of the categories independently you can clearly see the indicator that
335 requires more attention if it is an immediate action for its repair system 3 must be connected to system
336 1 for its performance, if it is an improvement that needs to be planned for future effect then it will
337 communicate it to system 4. This control exercised by system 3 will reveal the real health of the
338 system compared to its ideals and is of great impact to take the necessary actions so that the system
339 takes the course as planned, which contributes to its self-regulation.

340 System 2 is the one who transmits the information to system 3 and receives the results of the
341 operations carried out in system 1. Each objective described in system 4 is assigned a metric or
342 calculation formula to know the level of achievement of this, which is established in system 2. The

343 data to activate the formula or indicator correspond to the results of the tasks or activities developed
344 in System 1.

345 By capturing the information of the executed processes, the data are stored in system 2, where the
346 operation is carried out according to the established indicator or metric whose result allows us to have
347 a real idea of the behavior of the system based on the variables of integral sustainability evaluated.
348 Once captured, stored, and processed through calculations already programmed the real results of the
349 operations already executed are communicated to system 3 to proceed with the comparison according
350 to the goals. The information in system 2 will always be available in up-to-date or historical form for
351 future reference.

352 For its part, system 1 carries out all the basic operations or implementation of the initiatives necessary
353 for the system to function in general, operations corresponding to the biological and technical
354 processes of the sector given by the supply of raw materials, resource management, production, reuse,
355 collection, distribution, training processes, inclusion between according to the requests or
356 requirements received according to the variables of the integral sustainability of the sector
357 transmitting information of its results to system 2.

358 System 1 obeys the activities that were planned in system 4 and transmitted by system 3, in addition
359 to the interventions of the environment that require immediate action. Consequently, the environment
360 has a direct effect on systems 4 and 1 in the same way these systems interact directly with the external
361 environment.

362 **Organic principles of the holistic systemic causal model of** 363 **integral circular sustainability in the agri-food sector**

364 The sustainable model is given by four principles, as illustrated in Fig. 7, that facilitate the circularity
365 of the materials and inputs used in the production process of the agri-food sector, which allows

366 interaction with other processes and the collaboration of stakeholders in the sector as responsible for
 367 the work of minimizing negative impacts to the environment that affect society, the same process and
 368 the economy It is recognized that technologies must also be developed for this effect since it is she
 369 that affects the variable and not in the opposite way.

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371

Fig. 6 Basic principles of the sustainable model.

372 Fig. 8 represents a diagram in which the influence of the principles is observed once they are linked
 373 to the process, in which it is possible to consider that they create an effect on the categories of
 374 environment, economy, society and the process itself. Nevertheless, technology is what affects the
 375 principles, so they must be adapted or in favor of them.

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Fig. 7 Basic principles of the sustainable model integrated into the process.

379 Discussion

380 The variables environments, society and economy are those that by default are considered before the
381 studies of circularity and sustainability, but currently it is a framework that must expand and integrate
382 other variables that also require equal importance in front of these analyses for which technology and
383 processes are added, considering on the latter the life cycle of the products from the early stages of
384 their creation to the final disposal of the same.

385 Technology is important [28] due to its implication for the development of activities that will have
386 important consequences in the events that are executed from the sector under study that put their
387 sustainability at risk. Also, the processes leave traces that alter the life cycles within a region if they
388 are not studied in a systemic way considering their effects in the environment where they develop,
389 such a population and the very existence of the process are put at risk.

390 Knowing the variables and how they affect each other allows us to have a broad knowledge of the
391 sector detecting which is one that requires more attention after proceeding with the study can be a
392 voice of help to maintain the balance and not expose the integral sustainability of the sector.

393 The processes of the agri-food sector require attention from their nature, being some biological
394 necessary for planting and cultivation and the technicians who contribute to the advanced operations
395 of the same, it is pertinent to know how they flow and how these two variables of the process are
396 integrated, knowing that they have influences from the external environment from policies,
397 regulations, trends, markets and the environment itself but also the impacts to which they are exposed
398 and are able to exert on the internal media must also be considered, considering the internal policies
399 given by the mission, vision, values and internal regulations that regulate the relationship with other
400 internal processes [31].

401 This dynamic facilitates the analysis of the operations that need to be restructured and evidence their
402 incidence against the internal or external processes with which they have direct and indirect links,
403 which will help a better coexistence between them from the homeostasis of the system in general

404 [59]. Recognizing the effects on other processes allows the creation of awareness [25] that contributes
405 to the competitive and productive permanence of achieving objectives, remembering to be a
406 teleological process, that is, it has purpose and determination since it is not random, but planned and
407 premeditated [59], also with great impact on the economy, environment, interest groups, the
408 technological means to be used and on the same processes.

409 Holistic and adaptive dynamics of the agro-industrial sector based on Beer's viable model, integrating
410 the balanced scorecard as an iterative process that contributes to learning and continuous
411 improvement of the agro-industrial sector. Knowing the holistic dynamics is an increase in the
412 adaptability, viability and therefore the sustainability of the sector making it more economically,
413 technologically, socially, and environmentally responsible, preserving its integrity for future
414 generations and with good results that can be improved with the reasonable practices of the resources
415 available, being increasingly productive and efficient [14].

416 The fusion of systems analysis through the viable model of Beer and the balanced scorecard allows
417 us to conclude the strategic structure in a systemic way relevant for a better operation and achievement
418 of the established objectives. Considering the mission and vision of the system under study integrated
419 in system 5 of the model, in addition to this work items of interest that contribute to sustainability are
420 added, such as the learning that is generated, especially when an objective has indicators below the
421 established goal, which helps the approach of new and timely proposals for improvement to develop
422 in the short or long term.

423 The balanced scorecard designed from the viable system model of the sector under study allows the
424 evaluation of the variables of integral sustainability as an iterative process that contributes to the
425 learning and continuous improvement of the agro-industrial sector [60]. This interaction leads to the
426 creation of strategies [61] that should be included in the design from its link to the systemic process.
427 To go beyond determining low performance rates and proposing improvements is to recognize the
428 learning about what could not be achieved with the resources that were available.

429 The organic principles described for this model, such as use of circular material, recovery of
430 resources, extension of the useful life of the product, and collaborative work, are perceived as
431 necessary to guarantee the quality of the integral holistic sustainability of the system, so that its
432 integration is of value and in which its interaction with the main sustainability variables must be
433 considered, recognizing which affect the principles, but which in turn are affected by them [31,44,62].

434 In this opportunity, technology is key to compliance with the principles, and the use of artificial
435 intelligence is of great contribution to more efficient operations and results [38]; therefore, they are
436 also considered a restriction for the selection of this, since the application of the principles in the
437 model has a direct effect on the performance of this creating impact on the other categories of the
438 sustainable pentagon namely the environmental, social, economic and process, which are also
439 affected by technology. These last four do not affect the principles, but rather, they are affected if
440 they are not executed rationally and consciously.

441 **Conclusion**

442 This characterization the sector through causal map systemic, based on the determination of the
443 critical variables in terms of integral holistic sustainability, leads to creating a strategic structure from
444 the improvement and continuous learning of the sector as a complex adaptive system. Its value
445 focuses on permitting its location in the sustainable plane as a contribution to current global problems
446 from the systemic use of viable models that allows us to know three fundamental points:

- 447 ○ Knowing where the system is today by analyzing systems 1 (basic operations for normal
448 operation) and 2 (historical, current, and actual system information system) of the viable
449 systems model these systems are critical because they are part of the starting point to know
450 the path of improvement that the sector requires according to its objectives.
- 451 ○ Knowing where you want to go is another aspect of value that is estimated in system 3
452 (control system, audits where the ideal parameters and goals are established) the clarity of

453 the goals is important because they direct the processes of self-regulation of the system in
454 general.

455 ○ Knowing what is needed to reach that desired goal regarding the integral sustainable
456 performance of the sector so that it works internally and has a positive impact and adapts to
457 the external environment this is achieved in system 4 (system that allows future strategic
458 planning to better respond to the environment) considering the conditions or constraints of
459 system 5 (policy system, values, mission, vision that direct the system).

460 As an iterative process, it allows performance within the systemic approach of continuous
461 improvement and learning.

462 **Limitations and future research**

463 It is necessary to validate the integration model, in general, to identify with more solid criteria the
464 level of the contribution in the sector since it is a valuable contribution for policy management to
465 implement tools from the development of instruments in favor of the creation of comprehensive
466 strategies to reduce the negative impacts of certain economic and industrial activities, which represent
467 a critical issue for today's nations [63,64].

468 Respect to new research, the study of the synergy between and compensation between the economic
469 well-being of farmers, agricultural production and ecological preservation is considered [11], as well
470 as the lack of tools, methodologies, and frameworks to manage the increased complexity of agri-food
471 sustainability as a complex adaptive system [21]. Finally, the development of a model that quantifies
472 the level of depletion of resources due to their excessive use.

473 **Acknowledgment**

474 We gratefully thank the CONAHCYT for a scholarship and Secretaria de Investigación of Insituto
475 Politécnico Nacional for making possible the mobility to Luvis Paola Leon-Romero in the master

476 program. This work has been supported by the GOYA - Antonio Unanue in Engineering in the
477 Agrifood Industry Chair of the University of Seville (Spain) and the VII Own Research and Transfer
478 Plan 2023 of the University of Seville (Projects 2023/00000378 and 2023/00000390)

479 **Contributions**

480 L.L.R: conceptualization, investigation, data curation, formal analysis, writing, and editing.

481 F.P.Z: conceptualization, funding acquisition, formal analysis, and critical revisions.

482 A.L.S: conceptualization, funding acquisition, formal analysis, and revisions.

483 M.A.F: methodology, formal analysis, review, and supervision.

484 M.F.M: formal analysis, and critical revisions.

485 All authors critically helped in the interpretation of results, revised the manuscript, and provided
486 relevant intellectual input. They all read and approved the final manuscript.

487 **References**

- 488 1. Finanzas & I+D+i. Subvenciones para la agricultura en España: El secreto mejor Guardado.
489 In: Finanzas & I+D+i [Internet]. 18 Jul 2023 [cited 25 Sep 2023]. Available:
490 [https://finanzasidi.com/2023/07/18/subvenciones-para-la-agricultura-en-espana-que-son-](https://finanzasidi.com/2023/07/18/subvenciones-para-la-agricultura-en-espana-que-son-como-se-pueden-solicitar-y-que-beneficios-aportan/)
491 [como-se-pueden-solicitar-y-que-beneficios-aportan/](https://finanzasidi.com/2023/07/18/subvenciones-para-la-agricultura-en-espana-que-son-como-se-pueden-solicitar-y-que-beneficios-aportan/)
- 492 2. Cattaneo CA, Bocchicchio AM. Dinámica sociorganizacional en el sistema agroalimentario.
493 *Rev Mex Sociol.* 2019;1: 7–35.
- 494 3. Poponi S, Arcese G, Ruggieri A, Pacchera F. Value optimisation for the agri-food sector: A
495 circular economy approach. *Bus Strategy Environ.* 2022. doi:10.1002/bse.3274
- 496 4. Graham NT, Iyer G, Wild TB, Dolan F, Lamontagne J, Calvin K. Agricultural market
497 integration preserves future global water resources. *One Earth.* 2023;6: 1235–1245.
498 doi:10.1016/j.oneear.2023.08.003
- 499 5. Kheir AMS, Elnashar A, Mosad A, Govind A. An improved deep learning procedure for
500 statistical downscaling of climate data. *Heliyon.* 2023;9. doi:10.1016/j.heliyon.2023.e18200

- 501 6. Organización de las Naciones Unidas para la Alimentación y la Agricultura (FAO).
502 Agricultura Mundial Hacia los Años 2015/2030: Informe Resumido. Food and Agriculture
503 Organization of the United Nations, editor. Agricultura mundial: hacia los años 2015/2030.
504 2004. Available: [https://www.google.com.mx/books/edition/Agricultura_Mundial/qvr--](https://www.google.com.mx/books/edition/Agricultura_Mundial/qvr--cUhFcUC?hl=es&gbpv=1)
505 [cUhFcUC?hl=es&gbpv=1](https://www.google.com.mx/books/edition/Agricultura_Mundial/qvr--cUhFcUC?hl=es&gbpv=1)
- 506 7. Organización de las Naciones Unidas para la Alimentación y la Agricultura (FAO).
507 Agricultura Familiar en América Latina y el Caribe: Recomendaciones de Política. Salcedo S,
508 Guzmán L, editors. Santiago: Organización de las Naciones Unidas para la Alimentación y la
509 Agricultura; 2014. Available: www.fao.org/publications
- 510 8. Organización de las Naciones Unidas para la Alimentación y la Agricultura (FAO), Ediciones
511 Mundi-Prensa. The State of the World's Land and Water Resources for Food and
512 Agriculture. Managing systems at risk. Organización de las Naciones Unidas para la
513 Alimentación y la Agricultura (FAO), Mundi-Prensa, editors. Roma: Mundi-Prensa,
514 Organización de las Naciones Unidas para la Alimentación y la Agricultura (FAO); 2012.
- 515 9. Schneider JM, Zabel F, Schünemann F, Delzeit R, Mauser W. Global cropland could be
516 almost halved: Assessment of land saving potentials under different strategies and
517 implications for agricultural markets. PLoS One. 2022;17.
518 doi:10.1371/journal.pone.0263063
- 519 10. Rodríguez Eugenio N, McLaughlin M, Pennock D. La contaminación del suelo: una realidad
520 oculta. Roma; 2019.
- 521 11. Benabderrazik K, Kopainsky B, Tazi L, Joerin J, Six J. Agricultural intensification can no longer
522 ignore water conservation – A systemic modelling approach to the case of tomato
523 producers in Morocco. Agric Water Manag. 2021;256. doi:10.1016/j.agwat.2021.107082
- 524 12. Kuhmonen I, Kuhmonen T. Transitions through the dynamics of adaptive cycles: Evolution
525 of the Finnish agrifood system. Agric Syst. 2023;206. doi:10.1016/j.agsy.2023.103604
- 526 13. Manuel Alonso Cortés. El Análisis de Ciclo de vida y sus principales softwares como
527 herramientas de cálculo. In: Revista Digital Inesem. 20 Oct 2015.
- 528 14. Saxena P, Stavropoulos P, Kechagias J, Salonitis K. Sustainability assessment for
529 manufacturing operations. Energies (Basel). 2020;13. doi:10.3390/en13112730
- 530 15. de Carvalho Araújo CK, Bigarelli Ferreira M, Salvador R, de Carvalho Araújo CKC, Camargo
531 BS, de Carvalho Araújo Camargo SK, et al. Life cycle assessment as a guide for designing
532 circular business models in the wood panel industry: A critical review. J Clean Prod.
533 2022;355. doi:10.1016/j.jclepro.2022.131729
- 534 16. Scarpellini S, Valero-Gil J, Moneva JM, Andreaus M. Environmental management
535 capabilities for a “circular eco-innovation.” Bus Strategy Environ. 2020;29: 1850–1864.
536 doi:10.1002/bse.2472

- 537 17. Luqman M, Shahid T, Awan MUF, Kashif SUR, Arooj F, Awan AR. Quantification and
538 characterization of microplastics (MPs) pollution in peri-urban agricultural lands of
539 Lahore, Pakistan. *PLoS One*. 2023;18: e0291760. doi:10.1371/journal.pone.0291760
- 540 18. Aznar Sanchez JA, Mendoza JMF, Ingrao C, Failla S, Bezama A, Nemecek T, et al. Indicators
541 for Circular Economy in the Agri-food Sector. *Resour Conserv Recycl*. 2020;163: 105028.
542 doi:10.1016/j.resconrec.2020.105028
- 543 19. Rodríguez Aldabe Y. Potenciar la resiliencia de las ciudades y sus territorios de pertenencia
544 en el marco de los acuerdos sobre cambio climático y de la Nueva Agenda Urbana.
545 Santiago; 2018. Available: www.cepal.org/es/suscripciones
- 546 20. Sheppard P, Garcia-Garcia G, Stone J, Rahimifard S. A complete decision-support
547 infrastructure for food waste valorisation. *J Clean Prod*. 2020;247.
548 doi:10.1016/j.jclepro.2019.119608
- 549 21. Riemens M, Sønderskov M, Moonen AC, Storkey J, Kudsk P. An Integrated Weed
550 Management framework: A pan-European perspective. *European Journal of Agronomy*.
551 2022;133. doi:10.1016/j.eja.2021.126443
- 552 22. Pino-Vargas EM, Ascencios DR. Sustainability of olive cultivation under a climatological
553 approach in an arid region at the Atacama Desert. *Ciencia Tecnología Agropecuaria*.
554 2022;23. doi:10.21930/RCTA.VOL23_NUM3_ART:2652
- 555 23. Diogo V, Helfenstein J, Mohr F, Varghese V, Debonne N, Levers C, et al. Developing context-
556 specific frameworks for integrated sustainability assessment of agricultural intensity
557 change: An application for Europe. *Environ Sci Policy*. 2022;137: 128–142.
558 doi:10.1016/j.envsci.2022.08.014
- 559 24. Cook BR, Satizábal P, Curnow J. Humanising agricultural extension: A review. *World Dev*.
560 2021;140. doi:10.1016/j.worlddev.2020.105337
- 561 25. Allahyari MS, Sadeghzadeh M. Agricultural Extension Systems Toward SDGs 2030: Zero
562 Hunger. Springer. 2020. pp. 41–52. doi:10.1007/978-3-319-95675-6_2
- 563 26. Vermunt DA, Wojtynia N, Hekkert MP, Van Dijk J, Verburg R, Verweij PA, et al. Five
564 mechanisms blocking the transition towards ‘nature-inclusive’ agriculture: A systemic
565 analysis of Dutch dairy farming. *Agric Syst*. 2022;195. doi:10.1016/j.agsy.2021.103280
- 566 27. Howard M, Yan X, Mustafee N, Charnley F, Böhm S, Pascucci S. Going beyond waste
567 reduction: Exploring tools and methods for circular economy adoption in small-medium
568 enterprises. *Resour Conserv Recycl*. 2022;182. doi:10.1016/j.resconrec.2022.106345
- 569 28. Trabelsi M, Casprini E, Fiorini N, Zanni L. Unleashing the value of artificial intelligence in the
570 agri-food sector: where are we? *British Food Journal*. 2023;125: 482–515. doi:10.1108/BFJ-
571 11-2022-1014
- 572 29. Cañoles M, Valdés O, Rojas L, Galáz JC, Coz F, Díaz N, et al. Estudio de Economía Circular en
573 el Sector Agroalimentario Chileno. Santiago de Chile; 2019 Dec. Available:
574 <https://www.odepa.gob.cl/wp-content/uploads/2019/12/EstEconomiaCircular2019.pdf>

- 575 30. Poponi S, Arcese G, Mosconi EM, Di Trifiletti MA. Entrepreneurial drivers for the
576 development of the circular business model: The role of academic spin-Off. Sustainability
577 (Switzerland). MDPI; 2020. doi:10.3390/su12010423
- 578 31. Congreso nacional del medio ambiente. Retos del sector agroalimentario en los procesos
579 industriales. 2016.
- 580 32. Kiritsis D, Bufardi A, Xirouchakis P. Research issues on product lifecycle management and
581 information tracking using smart embedded systems. *Advanced Engineering Informatics*.
582 2003;17: 189–202. doi:10.1016/j.aei.2004.09.005
- 583 33. Monaga-Reina R, de-Las-Heras A, Luque-Sendra A, Lama-Ruiz JR. Improvement of
584 sustainability management through a plm structure. Good practices and a case study. *Dyna*
585 (Spain). 2021;96: 373–378. doi:10.6036/9915
- 586 34. Vila C, Abellán-Nebot J V., Albiñana JC, Hernández G. An Approach to Sustainable Product
587 Lifecycle Management (Green PLM). *Procedia Engineering*. Elsevier Ltd; 2015. pp. 585–592.
588 doi:10.1016/j.proeng.2015.12.608
- 589 35. Salonitis K, Stavropoulos P. On the integration of the cax systems towards sustainable
590 production. *Procedia CIRP*. Elsevier B.V.; 2013. pp. 115–120.
591 doi:10.1016/j.procir.2013.06.178
- 592 36. Kiritsis D. PLM and Product Embedded Information Devices. *IFAC Proceedings Volumes*.
593 2007;40: 8–23. doi:10.3182/20070523-3-ES-4908.00004
- 594 37. Tseng ML, Chiu ASF, Chien CF, Tan RR. Pathways and barriers to circularity in food systems.
595 *Resources, Conservation and Recycling*. Elsevier B.V.; 2019. pp. 236–237.
596 doi:10.1016/j.resconrec.2019.01.015
- 597 38. Krstić M, Agnusdei GP, Miglietta PP, Tadić S. Logistics 4.0 toward circular economy in the
598 agri-food sector. *Sustainable Futures*. 2022;4. doi:10.1016/j.sftr.2022.100097
- 599 39. Fiore M, Mongiello M. Blockchain Technology to Support Agri-Food Supply Chains: A
600 Comprehensive Review. *IEEE Acces*. 2016;4: 1–14. doi:10.1109/ACCESS.2017.DOI
- 601 40. Muñoz-Ulecia E, Bernués A, Briones-Hidrovo A, Casasús I, Martín-Collado D. Dependence
602 on the socio-economic system impairs the sustainability of pasture-based animal
603 agriculture. *Sci Rep*. 2023;13. doi:10.1038/s41598-023-41524-4
- 604 41. de Cunzo F, Petri A, Zaccaria A, Sbardella A. The trickle down from environmental
605 innovation to productive complexity. *Sci Rep*. 2022;12. doi:10.1038/s41598-022-25940-6
- 606 42. Poponi S, Arcese G, Pacchera F, Martucci O. Evaluating the transition to the circular
607 economy in the agri-food sector: Selection of indicators. *Resour Conserv Recycl*. 2022;176.
608 doi:10.1016/j.resconrec.2021.105916
- 609 43. Schöggel JP, Stumpf L, Baumgartner RJ. The narrative of sustainability and circular economy -
610 A longitudinal review of two decades of research. *Resources, Conservation and Recycling*.
611 Elsevier B.V.; 2020. doi:10.1016/j.resconrec.2020.105073

- 612 44. Pesce M, Tamai I, Guo D, Critto A, Brombal D, Wang X, et al. Circular economy in China:
613 Translating principles into practice. *Sustainability (Switzerland)*. 2020;12.
614 doi:10.3390/su12030832
- 615 45. Collado AD. La agricultura del futuro: cambios y desafíos. In: *La agricultura del futuro:
616 cambios y desafíos*.
- 617 46. Crippa M, Solazzo E, Guizzardi D, Monforti-Ferrario F, Tubiello FN, Leip A. Food systems are
618 responsible for a third of global anthropogenic GHG emissions. *Nat Food*. 2021;2: 198–209.
619 doi:10.1038/s43016-021-00225-9
- 620 47. Mies A, Gold S. Mapping the social dimension of the circular economy. *Journal of Cleaner
621 Production*. Elsevier Ltd; 2021. doi:10.1016/j.jclepro.2021.128960
- 622 48. Bassi AM, Bianchi M, Guzzetti M, Pallaske G, Tapia C. Improving the understanding of
623 circular economy potential at territorial level using systems thinking. *Sustain Prod Consum*.
624 2021;27: 128–140. doi:10.1016/j.spc.2020.10.028
- 625 49. Nyam YS, Kotir JH, Jordaan AJ, Ogundeji AA, Adetoro AA, Orimoloye IR. Towards
626 understanding and sustaining natural resource systems through the systems perspective: A
627 systematic evaluation. *Sustainability (Switzerland)*. 2020;12: 1–20.
628 doi:10.3390/su12239871
- 629 50. Dianat H, Wilkinson S, Williams P, Khatibi H. Planning the resilient city: Investigations into
630 using “causal loop diagram” in combination with “UNISDR scorecard” for making cities
631 more resilient. *International Journal of Disaster Risk Reduction*. 2021;65.
632 doi:10.1016/j.ijdr.2021.102561
- 633 51. Sterman John. *Business dynamics : systems thinking and modeling for a complex world*.
634 Irwin/McGraw-Hill; 2000.
- 635 52. León Romero LP, Aguilar Fernández M, Francisco Márquez M, Zamora Polo F, Luque Sendra
636 A. Characterization of the Information System Integrated to the Construction Project
637 Management Systems. SSRN. 2023. doi:http://dx.doi.org/10.2139/ssrn.4507812
- 638 53. Checkland P, Poulter J. *Soft Systems Methodology. Método Radical para Integrar
639 Actividades Organizativas*. Milrazones, editor. 2010.
- 640 54. Checkland P, Scholes J. *La Metodología de los Sistemas Suaves de Acción*. Grupo Noriega,
641 editor. Ciudad de México ; 1994.
- 642 55. Cummings S, Hassard J, Rowlinson M, Brocklesby J, Davies J. Demystifying the viable System
643 Model as a Tool for Organisational Analysis The end goal of management? View project A
644 New History of Management (with. Article in *Asia Pacific Journal of Operational Research*.
645 1995. Available: <https://www.researchgate.net/publication/266311839>
- 646 56. Aguilar Fernández M, Patiño Ortiz J, Jarquín BG, Fortanell Estrada P, Cedillo JA. The Viable
647 Systems Model: a Literature Review. *International Journal of Latest Research in Science and
648 Technology*. 2021;10: 34–36. doi:10.29111/ijlrst-2019-10968

- 649 57. Kaplan RS, Norton DP. *The Balanced Scorecard: Translating Strategy into Action*. 2nd ed.
650 *Gestión 2000*, editor. Barcelona: Harvard Business School Press; 2002. Available:
651 www.FreeLibros.me
- 652 58. Loewy T. El enfoque sistémico como criterio operativo y geográfico: La sostenibilidad
653 agrícola. *Estudios económicos*. 2021;38: 83–98. doi:10.52292/j.estudecon.2021.2300
- 654 59. Acosta Flores J. *Ingeniería de sistemas. Un enfoque interdisciplinario*. 2nd ed. Alfaomega
655 Grupo Editor S de CM, editor. Ciudad de México: Alfaomega Grupo Editor, SA de CV
656 México; 2017.
- 657 60. Farissi A, El Oumami M, Beidouri Z. Moroccan Agro-Food Companies: Performance
658 Evaluation through the Balanced Scorecard Method. *Int J Sup Chain Mgt*. 2020. Available:
659 <http://excelingtech.co.uk/>
- 660 61. Verdecho MJ, Pérez Perales D, Alarcón Valero F. Proposal of a Customer-Oriented
661 Sustainable Balanced Scorecard for Agri-Food Supply Chains. In: Springer C, editor.
662 Springer. Springer, Cham; 2020. pp. 233–240. doi:10.1007/978-3-030-44530-0_28
- 663 62. Yu. N K, A.V. U. Specific Features in Management of Agro-Food System Development Chair
664 of Information support and modeling of economic systems in agriculture. *Advances in*
665 *Economics, Business and Management Research*. 2020;147: 380–384.
- 666 63. Hjorth T, Huseinovic E, Hallström E, Strid A, Johansson I, Lindahl B, et al. Changes in dietary
667 carbon footprint over ten years relative to individual characteristics and food intake in the
668 Västerbotten Intervention Programme. *Sci Rep*. 2020;10. doi:10.1038/s41598-019-56924-8
- 669 64. Azimi MN, Rahman MM, Nghiem S. Linking governance with environmental quality: a global
670 perspective. *Sci Rep*. 2023;13. doi:10.1038/s41598-023-42221-y

671

672 **Supporting information**

673 S1 Appendix. Interaction and influence between the main variables of integral sustainability in the
674 agri-food sector

675

1 **Characterization and Causal Model of the Holistic Dynamics of the**
2 **Integral Sustainability of the Agrifood System**

3
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14 **APPENDIX S1**

15 **Interaction and influence between the main variables of integral sustainability in the**
16 **agri-food sector**

17 The present document is intended to explain the methodology used, which is the authors'
18 own, within the framework of the review of the literature consulted mainly on the Web of
19 Science and Scopus.

20 The table 1 shows the dynamic hypotheses used in the study, starting from an initial one
21 traditionally known in the sustainability cycle given by the linkage of economic, social and
22 environmental variables cycle 1.

23 Cycle 2 represents dynamic hypothesis 1 where process variables are integrated into the
24 traditional ones.

25 Cycle 3 represents dynamic hypothesis 2 where technology variables are integrated into the
26 traditional ones.

27 Finally, cycle 4 integrates both process and technology variables to the traditional ones,
 28 having a more integral interaction in the system under study.

29 **Table 1 Dynamic Hypotheses and system interactions**

Dynamic		
Hypotheses	Parameter	System Interaction
Cicle 1	Traditional model (Economy + environment + society)	-Creation of strategies to strengthen economic, social, and environmental links to guarantee future resources.
Cicle 2	Process + traditional model	-Specific controls on waste generating organizations. -Qualified procurement for efficient operations. -Reduction of costs and establishment of competitive market prices. -Selection of raw materials suitable for the process and the environment. -Generation of jobs with quality guarantees. [1,2]
Cicle 3	Technology + traditional model	-Encourages innovation. -Encourages the development of society. -Facilitates mechanisms that reduce environmental impacts. -Data and information management to support decisions. -Effort reduction. [3–5]
Cicle 4	Process + Technplogy + traditional model	-Improved transactions. -Security in processes. -Continuous monitoring of operations. -Reliable information for decision-making. -Use of eco-friendly and user-friendly tools, materials, and

	<p>methods.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> -Improved process flexibility and performance. -Trained staff to address issues [6–9]
--	--

30 **Level of interaction and influence between the main variables of integral**
 31 **sustainability in the agri-food sector**

32 The most commonly used sustainability variables or dimensions represent economy,
 33 environment and society, as evidenced in [9–17]. However, using this study, the following is
 34 annexed to this model: production and technology, therefore creating the so-called Pentagon of
 35 sustainability, as represented in Fig. 1.

36
 37 **Fig. 1 Integral sustainability pentagon**

38 Consider some internal variables, as shown in Fig. 2.

39

40 **Fig. 2 Variables of the integral sustainability of the agro-industrial sector**

41

42 **Objective**

43

44 Reinforce the sustainable structure by integrating variables that guarantee the supremacy and
 45 optimization of the use of resources, recognizing their importance and impact by the current
 46 economic and environmental crisis.

47 **Justification**

48

49 The methods and productive actions implemented, as well as the use and level of technologies
 50 applied, considerably affect the patterns of ecosystems according to their management,
 51 depleting resources or prolonging their useful life, which is of interest to explore since the
 aim is to avoid or slow down the extinction processes of certain reserves; therefore, it is
 necessary to incorporate variables that directly influence these dynamics [18–24].

51

52

Methodology

53 Phase 1: listing of system variables, Phase 2: description of relationships between system
 54 variables, and Phase 3: identification of key variables and their categories and interpretation.

55

Results

56

Table 2 List of variables to study

Environment	Society	Process	Technology	Economy
-------------	---------	---------	------------	---------

57

58

Table 3 Qualitative effect between variables

Integral Sustainability Variables	Process	Technology	Environment	Society	Economy
Process	Efficiency Productivity Performance.	It requires technology and encourages innovation for its development to contribute to efficient performance.	Emission of greenhouse gases, better use of water resources, soil degradation (extinguishes resources, rendering them worthless for future events) [15,25–32]	Provide opportunities for integration through interdisciplinarity within the framework of employability with quality. (direct-indirect/local or external contracting) [12,15,29,30,33]	Fair and affordable prices Investor-friendly profits investment level according to performance integration of productive sectors [5,15,34]

Technology	Generate agility in the processes. Optimal use of resources Avoid waste [9,31,35–41]	Ease of integration and achievement of goals.	Promote the consumption and rational use of resources, avoiding their deterioration or extinction [9,31]	Facilitates communications and relationships [9,37,38]	Streamlines transactions [9,31,36]
Environment	Soil and water quality interfere with the yield and efficiency. Availability of naturally occurring renewable and nonrenewable resources [34,42]	Need for mechanisms to clean, purify, and guarantee safe extractions.	Quality: air, water, land, availability of renewable and nonrenewable resources.	Air quality, water quality, safe disease-free environment [10,12,32,43,44]	Need for investment to remain stable and favorable [42,45]
Society	Professionalization for the optimal development of activities, sociocultural influence, and scale of consumption of goods and services produced [32,34,46]	Need for technology readiness [24,38]	Adequate use of resources to ensure their future availability [32,35]	Integration and participation, inclusive and resilient.	Opportunities for accessibility to services and products [12,44]
Economy	Cost of inputs, acquisition of credit, cost of taxes and tariffs, licenses, international stock exchange movements [47]	Procurement for development [48]	Grant investments for improvement and maintenance [31,35,47,49,50]	Enable resources to purchase goods and services (drives the economy itself)[34,44,48]	Development opportunities for everyone.
Very low	Low	Medium	High	Very high	
1	2	3	4	5	

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Table 4 Quantitative effect between variables

Integral Sustainability Variables	Process	Technology	Environment	Society	Economy	Variable that most affects
Process	5	4	5	4	4	22
Technology	5	5	4	4	4	22
Environment	5	2	5	3	2	17
Society	4	3	3	5	4	19
Economy	4	4	2	3	5	18
Variable that is most affected	23	18	19	19	19	

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Conclusion

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Establishing need in a variable indicates the level of dependence on the other variable, requiring contributions from it but not providing them. Put differently, it is critical for that variable to advance or evolve but does not promote a significant effect for the other variable. For example, it is important to have a healthy environment so as not to affect the quality of life or the health of society. However, the environment does not need highly specialized practices and society for its conservation because it requires more than the participation of society; other sectors would have to be linked since society uniquely would not cause a significant effect.

70

The matrix is filled in according to the answer to the question: is variable X (yellow column)

71

important for the progress or development of variable Y (blue row)?

72

The oblique line provides a qualifier of five, extensively corresponding to intersections between the same variables.

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- 75 1. Mies A, Gold S. Mapping the social dimension of the circular economy. *Journal of Cleaner*
76 *Production*. Elsevier Ltd; 2021. doi:10.1016/j.jclepro.2021.128960
- 77 2. Bassi AM, Bianchi M, Guzzetti M, Pallaske G, Tapia C. Improving the understanding of
78 circular economy potential at territorial level using systems thinking. *Sustain Prod Consum*.
79 2021;27: 128–140. doi:10.1016/j.spc.2020.10.028
- 80 3. Hackfort S. Unlocking sustainability? The power of corporate lock-ins and how they shape
81 digital agriculture in Germany. *J Rural Stud*. 2023;101. doi:10.1016/j.jrurstud.2023.103065
- 82 4. Kheir AMS, Elnashar A, Mosad A, Govind A. An improved deep learning procedure for
83 statistical downscaling of climate data. *Heliyon*. 2023;9. doi:10.1016/j.heliyon.2023.e18200
- 84 5. Zhang X, Wu K-S, He M. Concave-convex effect of financial resilience on corporate financial
85 performance: quantile regression approach. *Humanit Soc Sci Commun*. 2023;10: 654.
86 doi:10.1057/s41599-023-02169-w
- 87 6. Krstić M, Agnusdei GP, Miglietta PP, Tadić S. Logistics 4.0 toward circular economy in the
88 agri-food sector. *Sustainable Futures*. 2022;4. doi:10.1016/j.sftr.2022.100097
- 89 7. Manuel Alonso Cortés. El Análisis de Ciclo de vida y sus principales softwares como
90 herramientas de cálculo. In: *Revista Digital Inesem*. 20 Oct 2015.
- 91 8. de Carvalho Araújo CK, Bigarelli Ferreira M, Salvador R, de Carvalho Araújo CKC, Camargo
92 BS, de Carvalho Araújo Camargo SK, et al. Life cycle assessment as a guide for designing
93 circular business models in the wood panel industry: A critical review. *J Clean Prod*.
94 2022;355. doi:10.1016/j.jclepro.2022.131729
- 95 9. Sharma R, Kamble SS, Gunasekaran A, Kumar V, Kumar A. A systematic literature review on
96 machine learning applications for sustainable agriculture supply chain performance.
97 *Comput Oper Res*. 2020;119. doi:10.1016/j.cor.2020.104926
- 98 10. Kaklauskas A, Kaklauskienė L. Analysis of the impact of success on three dimensions of
99 sustainability in 173 countries. *Sci Rep*. 2022;12. doi:10.1038/s41598-022-19131-6
- 100 11. Wang Z, Liang F, Lin S-H. Can socially sustainable development be achieved through
101 homestead withdrawal? A hybrid multiple-attributes decision analysis. *Humanit Soc Sci*
102 *Commun*. 2023;10. doi:10.1057/s41599-023-02035-9
- 103 12. Ulukan D, Bergkvist G, Lana M, Fasse A, Mager G, Öborn I, et al. Combining sustainable
104 livelihood and farm sustainability approaches to identify relevant intensification options:
105 Implications for households with crop-based and gathering-based livelihoods in Tanzania.
106 *Ecol Indic*. 2022;144. doi:10.1016/j.ecolind.2022.109518
- 107 13. Vargas-Santander KG, Álvarez-Diez S, Baixauli-Soler S, Belda-Ruiz M. Developing a country's
108 sustainability indicator: An analysis of the effect on trade openness. *Environmental and*
109 *Sustainability Indicators*. 2023;19. doi:10.1016/j.indic.2023.100280

- 110 14. Huang R. SDG-oriented sustainability assessment for Central and Eastern European
111 countries. *Environmental and Sustainability Indicators*. 2023;19.
112 doi:10.1016/j.indic.2023.100268
- 113 15. Rossignoli CM, Manyise T, Shikuku KM, Nasr-Allah AM, Dompok EB, Henriksson PJG, et al.
114 Tilapia aquaculture systems in Egypt: Characteristics, sustainability outcomes and entry
115 points for sustainable aquatic food systems. *Aquaculture*. 2023;577.
116 doi:10.1016/j.aquaculture.2023.739952
- 117 16. Cordella M, Horn R, Hong SH, Bianchi M, Isasa M, Harmens R, et al. Addressing sustainable
118 development goals in life cycle sustainable assessment: Synergies, challenges and needs. *J*
119 *Clean Prod*. 2023;415. doi:10.1016/j.jclepro.2023.137719
- 120 17. Piwowar-Sulej K, Iqbal Q. Leadership styles and sustainable performance: A systematic
121 literature review. *J Clean Prod*. 2023;382. doi:10.1016/j.jclepro.2022.134600
- 122 18. Pitkänen K, Karppinen TKM, Kautto P, Pirtonen H, Salmenperä H, Savolahti H, et al. How to
123 measure the social sustainability of the circular economy? Developing and piloting social
124 circular economy indicators in Finland. *J Clean Prod*. 2023;392.
125 doi:10.1016/j.jclepro.2023.136238
- 126 19. Akinyi DP, Ng'ang'a SK, Ngigi M, Mathenge M, Girvetz E. Cost-benefit analysis of prioritized
127 climate-smart agricultural practices among smallholder farmers: evidence from selected
128 value chains across sub-Saharan Africa. *Heliyon*. 2022;8. doi:10.1016/j.heliyon.2022.e09228
- 129 20. MAO H, QUAN Y rong, FU Y. Risk preferences and the low-carbon agricultural technology
130 adoption: Evidence from rice production in China. *J Integr Agric*. 2023;22: 2577–2590.
131 doi:10.1016/j.jia.2023.07.002
- 132 21. Shi H, Kang Y, Ali MAS, Fan H. The influence of internet use on residents' ecological
133 conservation behaviors: Evidence from Taibai Mountain Nature Reserve, China. *Glob Ecol*
134 *Conserv*. 2023;46. doi:10.1016/j.gecco.2023.e02558
- 135 22. LI R, CHAI S xi, CHAI Y wei, LI Y wei, CHANG L, CHENG H bo. Straw strip mulching: A
136 sustainable technology for saving water and improving efficiency in dryland winter wheat
137 production. *J Integr Agric*. 2022;21: 3556–3568. doi:10.1016/j.jia.2022.08.098
- 138 23. Zegeye MB, Meshesha GB, Shah MI. Measuring the poverty reduction effects of adopting
139 agricultural technologies in rural Ethiopia: findings from an endogenous switching
140 regression approach. *Heliyon*. 2022;8. doi:10.1016/j.heliyon.2022.e09495
- 141 24. YUE M, LI W jing, JIN S, CHEN J, CHANG Q, Glyn J, et al. Farmers' precision pesticide
142 technology adoption and its influencing factors: Evidence from apple production areas in
143 China. *J Integr Agric*. 2023;22: 292–305. doi:10.1016/j.jia.2022.11.002
- 144 25. Chakraborti R, Davis KF, DeFries R, Rao ND, Joseph J, Ghosh S. Crop switching for water
145 sustainability in India's food bowl yields co-benefits for food security and farmers' profits.
146 *Nature Water*. 2023. doi:10.1038/s44221-023-00135-z

- 147 26. Yang J, Kang S, Chen D, Zhao L, Ji Z, Duan K, et al. South Asian black carbon is threatening
148 the water sustainability of the Asian Water Tower. *Nat Commun.* 2022;13.
149 doi:10.1038/s41467-022-35128-1
- 150 27. Piccoli I, Grillo F, Longo M, Furlanetto I, Ragazzi F, Obber S, et al. A farm-scale sustainability
151 assessment of the anaerobic digestate application methods. *European Journal of*
152 *Agronomy.* 2023;146. doi:10.1016/j.eja.2023.126811
- 153 28. Montanaro G, Doupis G, Kourgialas N, Markakis E, Kavroulakis N, Psarras G, et al.
154 Management options influence seasonal CO₂ soil emissions in Mediterranean olive
155 ecosystems. *European Journal of Agronomy.* 2023;146. doi:10.1016/j.eja.2023.126815
- 156 29. Han G, Niles MT. An adoption spectrum for sustainable agriculture practices: A new
157 framework applied to cover crop adoption. *Agric Syst.* 2023;212.
158 doi:10.1016/j.agsy.2023.103771
- 159 30. Robling H, Abu Hatab A, Säll S, Hansson H. Measuring sustainability at farm level – A critical
160 view on data and indicators. *Environmental and Sustainability Indicators.* 2023;18.
161 doi:10.1016/j.indic.2023.100258
- 162 31. Nti EK, Kranjac-Berisavljevic G, Doke DA, Wongnaa CA, Attafuah EE, Gyan MA. The impact
163 of artisanal gold mining on the sustainability of Ghana's river basins: The case of the Pra
164 basin. *Environmental and Sustainability Indicators.* 2023;19.
165 doi:10.1016/j.indic.2023.100264
- 166 32. Tourtelier C, Gorman M, Tracy S. Influence of gender on the development of sustainable
167 agriculture in France. *J Rural Stud.* 2023;101. doi:10.1016/j.jrurstud.2023.103068
- 168 33. Reidsma P, Accatino F, Appel F, Gavrilesco C, Krupin V, Manevska Tasevska G, et al.
169 Alternative systems and strategies to improve future sustainability and resilience of
170 farming systems across Europe: from adaptation to transformation. *Land use policy.*
171 2023;134. doi:10.1016/j.landusepol.2023.106881
- 172 34. Sarkodie SA, Owusu PA. Assessment of global fish footprint reveals growing challenges for
173 sustainable production and consumption. *Mar Pollut Bull.* 2023;194.
174 doi:10.1016/j.marpolbul.2023.115369
- 175 35. Ankrah DA, Anum R, Anaglo JN, Boateng SD. Influence of sustainable livelihood capital on
176 climate variability adaptation strategies. *Environmental and Sustainability Indicators.*
177 2023;18. doi:10.1016/j.indic.2023.100233
- 178 36. Tomar A. Sustainable photovoltaic based protective environment controlled farming
179 technology as economy boosters for agro-sectors. *Smart Agricultural Technology.* 2023;5.
180 doi:10.1016/j.atech.2023.100237
- 181 37. Dal Mas F, Massaro M, Ndou V, Raguseo E. Blockchain technologies for sustainability in the
182 agrifood sector: A literature review of academic research and business perspectives.
183 *Technol Forecast Soc Change.* 2023;187. doi:10.1016/j.techfore.2022.122155

- 184 38. Nurgazina J, Pakdeetrakulwong U, Moser T, Reiner G. Distributed ledger technology
185 applications in food supply chains: A review of challenges and future research directions.
186 Sustainability (Switzerland). MDPI AG; 2021. doi:10.3390/su13084206
- 187 39. Gkogkos G, Lourenço P, Pechlivani EM, Encarnação L, Votis K, Giakoumoglou N, et al.
188 Distributed Ledger Technologies for Food Sustainability indexing. Smart Agricultural
189 Technology. 2023;5: 100312. doi:10.1016/j.atech.2023.100312
- 190 40. Manzoor S, Dar AH, Dash KK, Pandey VK, Srivastava S, Bashir I, et al. Carbon dots
191 applications for development of sustainable technologies for food safety: A comprehensive
192 review. Applied Food Research. 2023;3. doi:10.1016/j.afres.2023.100263
- 193 41. Singh P, Kaur A. A systematic review of artificial intelligence in agriculture. Deep Learning
194 for Sustainable Agriculture. 2022; 57–80. doi:10.1016/B978-0-323-85214-2.00011-2
- 195 42. Malila BP, Kaaya OE, Lusambo LP, Schaffner U, Kilawe CJ. Factors influencing smallholder
196 Farmer’s willingness to adopt sustainable land management practices to control invasive
197 plants in northern Tanzania. Environmental and Sustainability Indicators. 2023;19.
198 doi:10.1016/j.indic.2023.100284
- 199 43. Caggiano H, Kocakuşak D, Kumar P, Tier MO. U.S. cities’ integration and evaluation of
200 equity considerations into climate action plans. npj Urban Sustainability. 2023;3.
201 doi:10.1038/s42949-023-00129-6
- 202 44. Orsango R, Rajan DS, Senapathy M, Bojago E. An analysis of rural farmers’ livelihood
203 sustainability in Offa district, Southern Ethiopia. J Agric Food Res. 2023;12.
204 doi:10.1016/j.jafr.2023.100610
- 205 45. Khan Z, Hossain MR, Badeeb RA, Zhang C. Aggregate and disaggregate impact of natural
206 resources on economic performance: Role of green growth and human capital. Resources
207 Policy. 2023;80. doi:10.1016/j.resourpol.2022.103103
- 208 46. Sun G, Lin X, Chen J, Xu N, Xiong P, Li H. Cultural inclusion and corporate sustainability:
209 evidence from food culture and corporate total factor productivity in China. Humanit Soc
210 Sci Commun. 2023;10. doi:10.1057/s41599-023-01649-3
- 211 47. Hidayati DR, Garnevska E, Childerhouse P. Enabling sustainable agrifood value chain
212 transformation in developing countries. J Clean Prod. 2023;395.
213 doi:10.1016/j.jclepro.2023.136300
- 214 48. Furszyfer Del Rio DD, Sovacool BK, Griffiths S, Foley AM, Furszyfer Del Rio J. A cross-country
215 analysis of sustainability, transport and energy poverty. npj Urban Sustainability. 2023;3.
216 doi:10.1038/s42949-023-00121-0
- 217 49. Kong L, Wu T, Xiao Y, Xu W, Zhang X, Daily GC, et al. Natural capital investments in China
218 undermined by reclamation for cropland. Nat Ecol Evol. 2023. doi:10.1038/s41559-023-
219 02198-3

220 50. Lou J, Hultman N, Patwardhan A, Mintzer I. Corporate motivations and co-benefit valuation
221 in private climate finance investments through voluntary carbon markets. npj Climate
222 Action. 2023;2: 32. doi:10.1038/s44168-023-00063-4
223